

ESTABLISHMENT OF SOVIET AUTHORITY IN BUKHARA

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Annotation: The Bolsheviks implemented a well-planned and well-thought-out tactic for ending the emirate’s rule in Bukhara and establishing Soviet government on its territory. As a result, the emirate was overthrown and passed to the young people of Bukhara under influence of the Bolsheviks.

The Bolsheviks showed a policy of colonialism from the earliest days of the formation of the BPSR. They tried to send the emirate’s treasury to the Center, to increase the number of Red Army, to punish and confiscate the poverty of large landowners who had worked during the Emir’s time. And they continued their actions with making a military-political agreement between Russia.

The government of the Bukhara People’s soviet Republic, under the leadership of Fayzulla Khodjayev, achieved significant success at the early times of 1923. Issues such as training of local staff and development of the education system were the most important aspects of Fayzulla Khodjayev’s activity. On March 11, 1921 with the initiative of F.Khodjaev, the Bukhara Council of people’s Ministers declared Uzbek (Turkish) language as a state language in the country. Special attention was paid to the training of national staff and their employment in the government agencies and various institutions. Because at that time, the Center regularly sent “experienced” staff to BPSR. In order to increase the role of local women in society resolution №183 was adopted on November 23, 1923. The main aim of this resolution was to create a fund to help local women.

After the October coup, the Bukhara Emirate and the Khanate of Khiva, which were considered protectorates of Tsarist Russia, became free and independent states, albeit for a short time. The Bolsheviks recognized the independence of these khanates only in name. However, soon their false policy proved to be the successor of Tsarist Russia.

The Bolsheviks soon began to end the rule of the Emirate in Bukhara and establish Soviet power on its territory. This military operation, which went down in history under the name "Bukhara operation", was carried out by the Red Army based on a careful plan developed in Moscow and Tashkent. According to the plan, on August 28, 1920, a revolution against the Emirate regime began in Old Chorjoi and quickly spread throughout Bukhara[1]. As previously agreed, the Charjoi Revolutionary Committee appealed to the Soviet government for help on the same day. According to the instructions of the Bolsheviks, the troops of the Red Army

invaded the territory of the sovereign Bukhara Emirate under the guise of helping the people of Bukhara. On September 2, 1920, Amir Olimkhan left the capital in order not to shed the blood of innocent people and prevent the destruction of sacred sites. As a result, the emirate system was overthrown in the country, and the power passed into the hands of young Bukharas influenced by the Bolsheviks. Administration On the pretext of helping the Provisional Government from the first day, 150 Bolsheviks arrived in Bukhara in search of leadership [2].

Under the guise of "supporting the creation of an independent democratic state in Bukhara" and under the pretext of preserving the "revolution" that was carried out by force with the help of the red soldiers' weapons, the Bolsheviks tried to divert all the socio-economic and political changes taking place here in the interests of Russia. they tried. In order to fulfill this task, according to the decision of the Turkish Commission on September 10, 1920, V. Kuybyshev was sent as a representative of the Government of the RSFSR, as well as the Central Committee of the RKP (b) in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic. On September 14, 1920, in Old Bukhara, at a joint meeting of the Central Revolutionary Committee of the CPSU, the Central Revolutionary Committee and the Council of People's Supervisors, V. Kuybyshev handed over his credentials to the head of the government of the USSR, F. Khojaev. During the presentation of the credentials, he noted that "the main demand of the RSFSR is to respect the independence of the state of Bukhara, to encourage all Russian citizens and organizations to respect the independence of Bukhara" [3]. This issue of the country's independence was stated in Article 3 of the Constitution of the USSR adopted in 1921 as follows: "The Republic of Bukhara People's Councils is recognized as an indivisible irkay (independent) state united within its present borders [4].

On October 6, 1920, the 1st Congress of All-Bukhara People's Representatives began its work in the summer palace of the Bukhara emir, Sitorai Mohi Khosa, and 1,960 delegates took part in it. The Kurultoi decided to declare Bukhara as the People's Soviet Republic (PSSR). From the first days of the formation of the USSR, the Bolsheviks demonstrated a policy of colonization. They took action to send the treasury of the Emirate to the Center, to increase the number of the Red Army, to confiscate and punish the property of large zamindars who operated during the time of the Emir, and to conclude a military-political agreement between the RSFSR [5].

In October-November 1920, a temporary military-political alliance and contract was concluded between the USSR and the RSFSR. On March 4, 1921, the Union Treaty was signed between the two countries. In November 1920, Article 2 of the agreement concluded between the two parties partially limited the internal independence of the USSR: "The factories and factories on these lands with all their tools and equipment will become the private property of the Bukhara Soviet

Republic. However, post and telegraphs, railways are not included in this article. Because this issue should be openly discussed and resolved within the framework of the Union" [6]. These agreements led to a certain degree of restriction of the activities of the young Bukhara state leaders who are trying to conduct independent politics. The alliance agreement "legally" justified the presence of Soviet troops on the territory of the independent state of Bukhara, which was nothing more than Russia's direct armed military intervention in the internal affairs of the USSR [7].

With the establishment of the USSR, the issue of the state language of the country became important. On March 11, 1921, on the initiative of Fayzulla Khojaev, the Bukhara People's Council of Supervisors announced the Uzbek (Turkish) language as the state language in the country. Information about this is also given in the official press of the government. "In the Republic of Bukhara People's Councils, the language of the majority of the people is Turkish, so their language was adopted as the official language. Today, the official language of the Republic of Bukhara People's Councils is Chigatay, which is based on Turkish" [8]. Unfortunately, although the Uzbek language was declared the official language in Bukhara, in practice official documents were kept in Russian. In some materials published in the press of that time, it was noted that meetings in state bodies and institutions were conducted in Russian, and although Turkish was often stated as the official language, it was not followed in practice [9].

Article 11 of the Constitution of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic stipulates that everyone should be educated in their native language: "confesses" [10]. However, the Uzbek language as a state language was not legally recognized in this constitution.

After the establishment of the BXSР, a number of intellectuals created secret organizations and their subsidiaries in order to "nationalize" the party and government bodies in order to ensure its true independence. In November 1920, Faizulla Khojaev appointed Munavvar Qari to the position of head of the foundation department in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic of Education. As a result, the center of the secret organization against the Soviet regime moved from Tashkent to Bukhara. In December 1920, with the arrival of Zaki Walidi in the city of Bukhara, the organization expands its activities, its members leave the territory of the Republic of Bukhara and move throughout the territory of Turkestan. While living in Bukhara, Walidy was actively involved in the organization of political parties inspired by the ideas of Jadidism, drawing up their programs and plans.

In 1921-1922, the movement against the Soviet regime in East Bukhara took a sharp turn. The reason for this was the invasion and looting carried out by the Red Army in this area. Red soldiers demanded food from the people here, punished innocent people, accused them of helping the "oppressors", and even went so far as to

touch the honor of women. This situation escalated in Kolob and Baljuvan, there was no government organization, and the population fled from their place of residence[11]. In December 1921, Osmankhoja, the chairman of the MIK of the USSR, was sent to this region to correct the situation in Eastern Bukhara. Osmankhoja, who saw with his own eyes his compatriots leaving their country and going to emigrate due to the disorder and arbitrariness of the Red soldiers, was strongly dissatisfied with the Soviet authorities. He opposed the presence of the Red Army in Bukhara and interference in the government's internal affairs. He sent a letter to Anwar Pasha, Ibrohimbek and other fighters of the independence movement in Eastern Bukhara, urging them to fight together against the Soviet regime. In addition, he tried to contact the British through Afghanistan in order to receive military assistance. However, when he did not achieve his goal, he lived in exile for a while in Afghanistan and then in Turkey until the end of his life.

In July 1922, the Central Emergency Investigation Commission of Bukhara discovered a secret national political organization opposed to the Soviet regime in Old Bukhara. This organization will be investigated for consolidating factions fighting against the existing political system, creating new factions through recruitment, supplying pro-independence factions with weapons and ammunition, and spying for the "printers".. Members of this national political organization were identified during the investigation. The head of this association is a person named Abdurrahman, who was the son-in-law of Amir Alim Khan. Also, Abdulahat Khan, one of the elders of the association, was a relative of the emir, and Mirza Bahram was a former mirza of the emir [12]. According to the decision of the Central Emergency Commission, ten of the leaders of the union were shot dead.

The policy of localization of state agencies of the Soviet government was implemented in the USSR as well as in other national republics. In August 1923, a localization commission was established under the Central Executive Committee of the USSR. In most archival documents and press materials, this commission is referred to as "Commission for Muslimization of Offices", and in some as "Commission for Indigenization of Offices".

The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Bukhara, at its plenum held on August 23, 1923, implemented the party's decision on the national issue, discussed the localization of state offices in the USSR and recommended changing the structure of the republic's government. As a result, the role of national personnel in the management of the republic was as follows: Porso Khojaev - chairman of the Central Executive Committee of the USSR; Ahmadjon Abdusaidov - secretary of the Central Executive Committee of the USSR; Faizulla Khojaev - Chairman of the Council of People's Supervisors; Ota Khojaev - Minister of Foreign Affairs, his deputy Komiljanov; Mukhtar Saidjonov - Inspector of Internal Affairs, his deputy

Giyosiddin Hasanov; Sattor Khojaev - People's Inspector of Financial Affairs; People's Inspector of Justice - Yusuf Zoda and his deputy Azimjon Sharipov; Abdurauf Fitrat - Minister of Education and his deputy Maskhoruddin Burkhanov; Choli Navrozov - People's Inspector of Land Affairs and his deputy Ghulam Kadyrov; Haji Hamro Yoldoshev - Inspector of State Control (Goskontrol) and his deputy Neprokin; Muinjon Aminov - Chairman of the Supreme Council of National Economy; Sadiq Muhammedov - the responsible secretary of the Central Committee of the Bukhara Communist Party and his secretaries - Pozdnishev and Naimjon Yakubzoda, Kori Yoldosh Polatov - the People's Inspector of Labor; Olimjon Okchurin - Member of the Labor People's Inspectorate; Rahmat Rafikov - Chairman of the Dictatorship Commission; Mullah Bolta - head of the Eastern Bukhara branch of the Emergency Commission; Sultanbekov - Chairman of the Bookkeeping Union and his deputy Arslan Khojaevlar [13] were noted.

By the decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Bukhara, government institutions were started to be filled with employees belonging to indigenous peoples. It was decided that 8% of European workers would be fired, leaving only 10-15% as managers[14]. At the same time as the process of localization of state offices was being carried out, the Bolshevik sent from the Center G.K. Ordzhonikidze expressed the following objection to the national composition of local cadres in the government of the USSR: "It is necessary to abandon the old idea that only Bukharans can hold the position of inspectors. I do not object to the Chairman of the Supervisory Council being a Bukhara, the Chairman of the Central Executive Committee of Bukhara being a Bukhara, but the secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Bukhara should not belong to the local nationality. Now the influence of such imagination is very noticeable. Get rid of it, get rid of it immediately. In the same way, it is necessary to give up the fact that the Soviet inspectors belong to the landed nation. Inspectors should not be chosen based on their nationality, of course, it is better for an inspector to be a Bukhara, but a Russian, Georgian or Tatar is better than Oripov" [15].

The government of the USSR and its leader, Faizulla Khojaev, tried to involve representatives of the local nationality as much as possible in the management work in the territory of the republic. F. Khojaev stated at the congresses of representatives of the Turkmen, Kazakh and Tajik peoples that "it is necessary to secure the rights of the small nations and tribes living in our republic in order to improve our state structure" [16]. Also, in his opinion, representatives of local population such as couriers, janitors, permanent mirzas, heads of economic departments, junior mirzas, bookkeepers, etc. and should have been from Kyrgyz.

Training of military personnel from local youth in the USSR was also considered one of the urgent tasks facing the government. The first Bukhara military

school, established in February 1921, introduced the following procedure for local youth who wanted to study. The age of those who are recruited to this military school must be between 18 and 26 years old, and according to official requests up to 30 years old, they must be in good health and have a recommendation from the party, union or government institutions. It is also stated that it is not necessary to be a Muslim and literate in Russian to enter the military school. The procedure for providing this military school with specialist teachers, textbooks and training manuals and teaching in the Muslim language has been established [17].

During this period, attention was paid to the training of local women workers. At the First All-Bukhara Congress, the issue of women's work was raised, but it was rejected. At the Second Congress, the party raised this issue again and it was approved. In the third congress, rights were given regarding the involvement of women in government offices. At the fourth congress, 1 woman was approved as a member of Bukhara MIK. Two-month training courses for volost organizers were organized under the women's department of the Central Committee of Bukhara. As a result, 55 women in Bukhara graduated from the volost organizer course [18].

Resolution No. 183 was adopted on November 23, 1923 in order to increase the role of local women in society [19]. In the decision, it was proposed to create a fund aimed at helping local women. On the basis of this fund, the protection of mothers and children and the involvement of women in artels, model workshops, clubs, schools and various institutions have been established.

The head of the government of the USSR F. Khojaev and a group of national leaders faced hundreds of problems such as solving the intractable problems in the republic, protecting national interests while getting rid of the tricks of the Center, gaining independence, and returning refugees to their countries. standing Among such problems, the issue of localization of personnel was also considered important. Because at this time "experienced" personnel were regularly sent from the Center.

Summary. After the overthrow of the Bukhara Emirate by the Red Army and the creation of the USSR, its independence was practically limited. Many problems arose as a result of the Soviet state's attempt to steer the newly created young republic. The head of the government of the USSR Fayzulla Khojaev and a group of national leaders have done exemplary work in the localization of state agencies. Conducting work in Uzbek, establishing a localization commission, involving representatives of indigenous peoples in the lower and upper management bodies of the government were practical steps in this regard.

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